

ASSESSMENT OF THE EFFECTS OF PROCESS-INDUCED STRESSES ON SOME MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF CARBON/EPOXY LAMINATES BY ACOUSTIC EMISSION

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ABSTRACT: This study is directed towards analysing the effects of process-induced stresses upon some mechanical characteristics of carbon/epoxy laminates, i.e. tensile properties. The use of acoustic emission during tensile tests enables to assess the effects of process-induced stresses upon laminates failure mechanisms. The first-ply failure in composites is affected by thermally-induced residual curing stresses and is frequently used as a method to determine residual stresses in symmetrical laminates [1 - 4]. In this study, process-induced stresses are on the one hand computed thanks to a thermoviscoelastic model including laminate/tool-plate interaction [5] and on the other hand measured using a layer removal technique (for symmetrical laminates) and room-temperature shape of $[0^{\circ}_2/90^{\circ}_2]$ laminated strips. A comparison between theoretical and experimental results is made and the influence of residual stresses is analysed. To this end, several UD, cross-ply and angle-ply ($\theta = 45^{\circ}$) laminates were manufactured according to three different cure cycles. These cure cycles were designed to produce different levels of process-induced stresses. The three different cure cycles enable to manufacture laminates for which T_g and matrix degree of cure α determined at the end of cure keep the same values. The cooling rate = $3^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ for all cure cycles. All the laminates are ply-by-ply precompacted before curing and the pressure path is always the same. Consequently, the laminates are void-free. Mechanical tests are performed on $[0^{\circ}_{16}]$, $[90^{\circ}_{16}]$, $[\pm 45^{\circ}_4]_s$ and $[0^{\circ}_2/90^{\circ}_2]_s$ samples. Tensile samples are equipped with four acoustic emission sensors. Tests performed on UD samples enable to correlate acoustic signals to applied stresses and induced damages.

KEY-WORDS: residual curing stress, processing, acoustic emission, mechanical properties.

INTRODUCTION

As it has already been mentioned in a previous work [TAR 02], comparing the whole literature about residual process-induced stresses with the number of public papers which offer an analysis of the influence of these stresses upon the laminates' mechanical characteristics, clearly shows that only a few authors have dedicated their research work to this specific point. From 1979, R.Y. Kim and H.T. Hahn [1] have studied the first-ply failure taking the residual curing stresses into consideration. The method that they developed at that time has since then extensively been re-used for the experimental determination of residual stresses' level in cross-ply laminates [2-4]. More recently, some authors have reached the conclusion that the linear behaviour of laminated composites does not seem to be affected by residual curing stresses [6] and have shown that these stresses however affect the non-linear part of laminates' behaviour and plasticity parameters. From a micromechanical point of view, the presence of residual curing stresses at fibre/matrix interface has been both modelled [7] and also integrated into the analysis of single fibre pull-out tests [8, 9]. Still from a micromechanical point of view, residual stresses' distribution has been studied by Raman spectroscopy. This has enabled A. Papeitis and Galotis to show how residual curing stresses modify fibre/matrix interfacial failure scheme at room temperature [10]. Among all this literature, our work has consisted in analysing a few aspects of the mechanical behaviour (tensile moduli and ultimate strengths) of various laminates undergoing different levels of residual curing stresses. To this end, mechanical tests were performed according to European standards on simple stacking sequences laminates. The various events occurring during tensile tests such as matrix cracking, interlaminar delamination, fibres breakage, etc., were recorded owing to an acoustic emission device.

MANUFACTURING CONDITIONS

The material used for this study is an unidirectional carbon/epoxy prepreg tape manufactured by Hexcel-Composites France. Its commercial reference is T2H132 300 EH25 34%. All the manufactured laminates were, prior to curing, ply-by-ply precompacted under vacuum and then vacuum-bag cured in our laboratory's autoclave (closed-loop control - up to 32 thermocouples embedded in the laminated parts) according to three different cure cycles. These cure cycles were designed to produce different levels of residual curing stresses while all the physical properties of the laminates were imperatively kept constant. In other words, this means that the temperature route of the cure cycles was modified as shown in fig. 1, while respecting the following constrained functions:

- matrix degree of cure α measured by DSC: $97\% \leq \alpha \leq 99\%$
- matrix glass transition temperature T_g measured by DSC: $150 \leq T_g \leq 154^\circ\text{C}$
- fibre volume fraction $V_f\%$ maximum allowed change
for laminates having identical stacking sequences: $\Delta V_f \% = \pm 0,2\%$
- void content (volume fraction) $V_v\%$: $V_v = 0\%$

For all the cure cycles carried out in this study, the bagging products and especially the releasing agent (between laminates' bottom ply and tool-plate) were unchanged. Three temperature routes were designed on the basis of a consolidated cure kinetics (more than ten years results obtained by DSC on T2H132 300 EH25 prepreg). As shown in fig. 1, it is simply the difference between curing dwell and room temperature that will generate differences in the levels of residual curing stresses. In fact, some other parameters such as cooling rate could have been modified instead of changing the temperature route to produce changes in residual stresses level. Nevertheless, as it has been shown in a sensitiveness study [5] — this study is similar to those performed in references [11, 12] — modifying the cooling rate between the limits achievable by our autoclave (i.e. $0.5 \rightarrow 5^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$) does not produce sufficient changes in the level of residual curing stresses in, for example, cross-ply laminates. Lastly, concerning the three cure cycles that were designed to change the level of residual stresses, it is important to mention that besides the cure cycle recommended by the prepreg manufacturer, the technical data sheet of T2H 132 300 EH25 prepreg also gives three variant of equivalent cure cycles. The cure cycle with the 160°C - 480 minutes curing dwell is one of these variations, while the cure cycle with 200°C - 40 minutes curing dwell is a only a result of the cure kinetics.

Fig. 1 The three equivalent cure cycles (equivalent in terms of degree of cure and matrix T_g).

It is important to mention that in order to avoid any effects of moisture absorption, all the manufactured laminates are stored in sealed bags with a desiccating agent.

PHYSICAL CHARACTERISATION

Table 1 shows the results of the various physical characterisations carried out on samples cut out from $[0^\circ_{16}]$, $[0^\circ_2/90^\circ_2]_s$ and $[\pm 45^\circ_4]_s$ laminates. This physical characterisation campaign has been performed immediately after laminates curing (exactly within one week after curing).

Cure cycle curing dwell		Matrix degree of cure α (measured by DSC)	Matrix Tg (°C) (measured by DSC)	Matrix Tg (°C) (measured by TMA)
Temperature (°C)	Duration (min)			
160	480	0.972	153.6	154
180	120	0.982	153.8	155
200	40	0.985	150.0	152

Table 1 Results of physical characterisation campaign carried out on samples autoclave cured at 160, 180 or 200°C.

Concerning fibre volume fraction $V_f\%$, chemical dissolution tests were performed on rectangular coupons (at least 6) cut out from $[0^\circ_{16}]$, $[0^\circ_2/90^\circ_2]_s$ and $[\pm 45^\circ_4]_s$ laminates. The obtained results are reported in table 2. As it can be seen in table 2, the constrained function on fibre volume fraction stated in the introduction of this paper has been fully respected.

Cure cycle	Laminate stacking sequence	Laminate thickness (mm)	$V_f\%$
160°C - 480 min	$[0^\circ_{16}]$	1.99	66.0
	$[0^\circ_2/90^\circ_2]_s$	2.04	63.8
	$[\pm 45^\circ_4]_s$	2.02	64.0
180°C - 120 min	$[0^\circ_{16}]$	1.98	65.8
	$[0^\circ_2/90^\circ_2]_s$	2.02	64.0
	$[\pm 45^\circ_4]_s$	2.03	64.1
200°C - 40 min	$[0^\circ_{16}]$	1.98	65.8
	$[0^\circ_2/90^\circ_2]_s$	2.01	64.1
	$[\pm 45^\circ_4]_s$	2.02	64.1

Table 2 Laminates thickness and $V_f\%$ as functions of cure cycle and stacking sequence.

As a summary, it can be said that this physical characterisation campaign clearly shows the equivalence between the three cure cycles, since laminates' matrix degree of cure α remains constant and T_g values lie between the allowed limits. Furthermore, if one considers laminates which have the same stacking sequence, curing these laminates at 160, 180 or 200°C does not induce any changes in $V_f\%$. Consequently, none of the changes that could be detected in their mechanical behaviour will be due to a modification of their physical characteristics.

RESIDUAL CURING STRESSES

1. Modelling and theoretical predictions

For each one of the manufactured laminates, the residual curing stresses were theoretically determined according to the procedure schematized in fig. 2. All the details of calculations can be found in ref. [5]. The laminates characteristics are not described as a function of matrix degree of cure α , since, as previously explained in the "manufacturing conditions" paragraph and as shown in table 1, the whole study has been performed at a constant value of α . In addition, from an industrial point of view, laminated parts for primary mechanical structures are generally manufactured with the aim of getting a degree of cure as high as possible.

2. Experimental determination of residual stresses

Two experimental methods were used to determine the level of residual curing stresses. First, during each cure cycle, unsymmetrical $[0^\circ_2/90^\circ_2]$ laminated strips were manufactured. Their initial in-plane dimensions (before curing) were 200 mm x 20 mm. Immediately after curing, the out-of-plane

deflection of these laminated strips was measured using a profile projector. Figure 3 (bottom diagram) shows the obtained results (grey dots) compared with theoretical curvature values (straight line) given by our specific modelling (described in fig.2). Figure 3 (upper diagrams) also gives predicted residual stresses distributions in $[0^\circ_2/90^\circ_2]$ and $[0^\circ_2/90^\circ_2]_s$ laminates. As it can be seen in fig.3 top diagram, increasing curing dwell temperature from 160°C up to 200°C results in an increase by 28% in σ_{xx} . σ_{xx} is the residual stress according $[0^\circ_2/90^\circ_2]_s$ laminates x axis (either in 0° or in 90° plies). Consequently, it can be said that the effect of curing dwell temperature modification upon residual stresses appears clearly. The same conclusion applies to the out-of-plane deflection (characterised by a reduced curvature) after curing of $[0^\circ_2/90^\circ_2]$ laminates. Indeed, fig.3 middle and bottom diagrams clearly show the effects of curing dwell temperature upon the residual stresses in these laminates and their room-temperature curvature.

Fig. 2 Theoretical prediction of residual curing stresses.

The second method used here is the ply removal analysis [4, 14]. On the one hand, this enables the distribution of residual stresses in symmetric (and balanced) laminates to be assessed and on the other hand, the layer removal method enables to show, as it can be seen in fig. 4, that the three cure cycles do produce different levels of residual curing stresses. The $[0^\circ_2/90^\circ_2]_s$ laminates were abraded according to a specific experimental procedure. Laminates are water-cooled during the abrasion to avoid any increase in temperature that could induce a matrix degradation or an acceleration of the relaxation process as believed in ref. [15]. Once the desired thickness has been removed, the laminates are placed in an oven at 100°C in order to remove any water absorbed during the abrading. A thickness equivalent to up to three plies is thus removed from the $[0^\circ_2/90^\circ_2]_s$ laminates, thus leaving (at the end of the procedure) unsymmetrical $[90^\circ_3/0^\circ_2]$ laminates.

Fig. 3 Theoretical level of residual stresses in $[0^\circ_2/90^\circ_2]_s$ and $[0^\circ_2/90^\circ_2]$ laminates and comparison between experimental and theoretical reduced curvature values.

The out-of-plane curvature of these $[90_3/0_2]$ laminates is then measured using a profile projector and the residual stress distribution is determined (fig. 4).

Fig. 4 Residual stresses distribution determined from the measurement of the curvature created by layer removal method on initially symmetrical $[0_2/90_2]_s$ laminates cured at 160, 180 or 200°C.

TENSILE TESTS AND ACOUSTIC EMISSION

1. Acoustic emission device

Tensile tests have been performed on a 8561 INSTRON according to conditions described in European standards EN 2561 and EN 2597. An exception has been made about the displacement speed of the INSTRON moving crosshead. A 0.5 mm/min speed was used instead of a 2 mm/min speed recommended in the standards. Lowering the crosshead displacement speed enables both to make a more accurate distinction between the acoustic events and to stop the tensile test when a given load is reached. The acoustic emission device is schematised in fig. 5. As it can be seen, the tensile test samples were all equipped with four piezoelectric sensors. Two of them are located near the sample end-tabs in order to eliminate noise signals coming from end-tabs and INSTRON jaws.

2. Mechanical behaviour of $[0_{16}]$ samples and acoustic emission

Mechanical tests have been performed on samples cut out from $[0_{16}]$ laminates cured according to each of the three cure cycles (cf. fig.1). Each kind of mechanical test has been performed on at least 10 samples. Figure 6 shows the typical behaviour of $[0_{16}]$ samples during a tensile test depending on their curing temperature. The left side of fig. 6 is a plot of the strain versus stress curves, while the right side exhibits the acoustic emission results. The acoustic emission diagrams show both the magnitude of the acoustic signals and the energy released by the sample during the tensile test. Magnitude and energy are plotted versus the tensile load applied to the laminated sample. In addition, the fact of knowing samples cross-section enables to convert the tensile load scale into a tensile stress scale. This conversion has not been performed directly on the acoustic emission diagrams but is nevertheless used in our various comments hereafter.

If it remains difficult to notice any difference in the elastic behaviour (i.e. longitudinal tensile moduli E_{xx}), it can be seen that the longitudinal ultimate tensile strength (denoted by σ_{xx}^{ult}) depends on the curing dwell temperature. To make mechanical behaviour more explicit, a synthesis table is included in fig.6. This table gives moduli E_{xx} and σ_{xx}^{ult} average values depending on curing dwell temperature and duration. It shows that the average σ_{xx}^{ult} of $[0_{16}]$ laminates cured 20 min at 200°C is about 15% higher than the average σ_{xx}^{ult} of $[0_{16}]$ laminates cured 480 min at 160°C. The changes recorded in E_{xx} between the two cure cycles (160 and 200°C) are lower than 6%. One must bear in mind that modulus measurement uncertainty which is only about 0.46%.

Fig. 5 Acoustic emission device used during tensile tests

Concerning acoustic emission, only the results relative to laminates cured 480 min at 160° and 40 min at 200°C are reported on the right side of fig.6. It can be seen that from the very beginning of the tensile tests the magnitude of acoustic signals increases quickly to reach the level of 70dB. Whatever the cure cycle is, 70dB signals are recorded for a tensile stress of about 180 MPa. The first signals for which the magnitude reaches 90dB appear for a 250 MPa tensile stress when samples are cured at versus 550 MPa when samples are cured at 200°C. As shown in several refs. [16, 17], 70dB signals can be associated to fibre/matrix debonding and 90 dB (or higher) signals to carbon fibres breakage.

Fig. 6 Results of tensile tests and acoustic emission on $[0^\circ_{16}]$ samples. The table gives moduli and ultimate strengths average values depending on curing dwell temperature and duration.

3. Mechanical behaviour of $[90^\circ_{16}]$ samples and acoustic emission

The results of tensile test performed on $[90^\circ_{16}]$ samples are reported in fig. 7. The left side of fig.7 represents the typical mechanical behaviour of these samples during the tests. As it has been made for $[0^\circ_{16}]$ laminates, the main parameters of the tensile behaviour of $[90^\circ_{16}]$ are synthesised in the table included in fig. 7. Finally, acoustic emission results are reported in fig. 7 right side.

Fig. 7 Results of tensile tests and acoustic emission on $[90^\circ_{16}]$ samples. The table gives moduli and ultimate strengths average values depending on curing dwell temperature and duration.

The transverse tensile modulus E_{yy} do not seems to depend on curing temperature. The average changes in E_{yy} between the laminates cured at 160°C and those cured at 200°C do not exceed 2%. The transverse ultimate tensile strength $\sigma_{yy}^{ult.}$ is more sensitive to different cure cycles. A 14% increase in $\sigma_{yy}^{ult.}$ is recorded between laminates cured for 480 min at 160 and those cured for 40 min at 200°C. Whatever the cure cycle is, all the acoustic signals remain below 70dB. As expected this shows that $[90^\circ_{16}]$ samples failure occurs without any fibre breakage and in addition without any fibre/matrix debonding if it is hypothesised that 70dB corresponds to this phenomenon (as shown in refs. [16, 17]). As a summary, the transverse ultimate tensile strength $\sigma_{yy}^{ult.}$ appears to be higher for laminates cured at 200°C than for those cured at 160°C while the residual stresses (from a micromechanical point of view) are lower in laminates cured at 160°C than in those cured at 200°C. An explanation could be found in ref. [7]. Effectively, as shown in ref. [7], when the critical normal stress on fibre/matrix interface is small, the ultimate tensile strength of $[90^\circ_n]$ laminates increase together with the level of residual curing stresses. This is what it can be seen with our results on $[90^\circ_{16}]$ laminates which confirm T. Ishikawa's conclusion on off-axis strength of UD laminates [7]. However, the problem to solve on this particular point, is that acoustic emission diagrams (fig. 7) do not exhibit any signal equal to or higher than 70dB the magnitude at which fibre/matrix debonding occurs !

4. Mechanical behaviour of $[0^\circ_2/90^\circ_2]_s$ samples and acoustic emission

The obtained results are reported in fig. 8. Symmetrical cross-ply laminates exhibit a tensile behaviour which clearly depends on the curing conditions (as shown by the stress versus strain curves in the upper left side of fig. 8) and therefore on residual curing stresses level. Between $[0^\circ_2/90^\circ_2]_s$ laminates cured for 480 min at 160°C and those cured for 40 min at 200°C, the x axis (0° plies orientation) tensile modulus increases by more than 8%. Similarly, the ultimate tensile strength according to x axis grows by 15%. When referring to table 1, it can be noticed that physical characteristics (i.e. T_g and degree of cure α) are almost constant whatever the cure cycle is. This is the consequence of the constrained functions used to design the cures cycles. Moreover, table 2 shows that for $[0^\circ_2/90^\circ_2]_s$ laminates, the fibre volume fraction undergoes a maximum 0.5% variation when changing the curing conditions. Applying the rule of mixtures and classical laminated plates theory enables to show that for $[0^\circ_2/90^\circ_2]_s$ laminates a theoretical increase by 0.5% in $V_f\%$ results in a theoretical 0.75% growth in the apparent tensile modulus E_{xx} . This means that the 8% changes in E_{xx} recorded here during the tensile tests, cannot be exclusively ascribed to the small variations in $V_f\%$ generated by the different cure cycles. Eliminating the changes in T_g and α which are extremely low and showing that the small variations in $V_f\%$ alone cannot generate the 8% changes in E_{xx} , enables to say that these changes are

due to the changes in residual curing stresses (see fig. 3). The same is true for ultimate stresses. In consequence, when correlating fig. 3 (upper diagram) and tensile test results it appears that both modulus and ultimate tensile strength increase with increasing residual stress level.

Fig. 8 Results of tensile tests and acoustic emission on $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_s$ samples. The table gives moduli and ultimate strengths average values depending on curing dwell temperature and duration.

5. Mechanical behaviour of $[\pm 45^\circ]_s$ samples and acoustic emission

The obtained results are reported in fig. 9. As shown by results reported in the table located in fig. 9 (left side), shear modulus and ultimate strength are higher for laminates cured at 160°C than for those cured at 200°C. In that case, the mechanical response of the $[\pm 45^\circ]_s$ samples is dominated by shear effects (σ_{12} shear stress in principal material coordinates — see ref. [18]) and, as shown by the stress versus strain curves in fig.9, large inelastic strains. As expected and shown in the right side of fig. 9 the laminate failure occurs without any fibre breakage, since none of the acoustic signals reach and go beyond 90dB.

Fig. 9 Results of tensile tests and acoustic emission on $[\pm 45^\circ]_s$ samples. The table gives moduli and ultimate strengths average values depending on curing dwell temperature and duration.

Let's now assume (as previously made) that for our laminates a 70dB magnitude (as shown in refs. [16, 17]) effectively corresponds to fibre/matrix debonding.

In that case, for laminates cured at 160°C or at 200°C, the very firsts fibre/matrix debondings occur respectively for a 210 and a 180 MPa mechanical tensile stress (see fig. 9 right side).

For analysis reasons, the residual stress distribution in $[\pm 45^\circ_4]_s$ laminates predicted according to fig.2 procedure and ref. [5] modelling has been plotted in fig. 10. The stresses are given in the laminate's global coordinates system. It can be seen that $+45^\circ/-45^\circ$ interfaces undergo a 35 MPa residual stress according laminate x axis when the laminates are cured for 480 min at 160°C versus 45 MPa when they are cured for 40 min at 200°C.

Consequently, this shows that angle-ply tensile test is the loading case for which the influence of residual curing stresses upon the laminates ultimate strength appears the more clearly. Indeed, increasing the residual stress level at $+45^\circ/-45^\circ$ interfaces by changing the curing conditions results in a weakening of $[\pm 45^\circ_4]_s$ laminates, as shown by the experimental results (fig. 9).

Fig. 10 Residual stresses theoretical distribution through $[\pm 45^\circ_4]_s$ laminates thickness. Residual stresses are plotted depending on the curing dwell temperature (160, 180 or 200°C).

CONCLUDING REMARKS

Without performing any further analysis, this first work enables to show a few elements of the relations between residual curing stresses and some mechanical characteristics of simple stacking sequence laminates. The results synthesised in this paper must obviously be examined in more details. Results concerning UD laminates behaviour must, in particular, be analysed together with the predictions of residual stresses on a micromechanical level. On this account, a closer correlation with ref. [7] semi-micromechanical modelling could be made in the future. However, the problem encountered with micromechanical modelling is that a critical normal stress on fibre/matrix interface is frequently used to predict the off-axis ultimate strength of UD laminates. But, in our experimental work, acoustic emission results show that none of the $[90^\circ_{16}]$ undergo fibre/matrix debonding during the tensile tests and this until their failure...

In fact, from a theoretical point of view, the predicting the distribution of residual curing stresses and integrating them into a failure criterion has been made possible (see ref. [1, 2] for example). Nevertheless, we think that the main difficulty is located on the experimental level. Indeed, the difficulty is the manufacturing of laminates for which only the level of residual stresses is modified while keeping constant all the physical (i.e., matrix T_g , matrix degree of α , laminate thickness, $V_f\%$, void content, ...) characteristics remain absolutely constant. This is what has been tried in this work.

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